

IN PARTICULAR THE ROLE OF CERTAIN LAXEMAS IN ART HISTORICAL DISCOURSE

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Abstract: this article discusses the importance of certain lexemes in the historical discourse and the writer Muhammad Ali's method of using historical words in his novels, his unique approach to word selection.

Key words: historical discourse, archaism, historicism, ethnonym.

Usually, in order to distinguish individuals from each other, their names are used together with descriptors that are named based on certain characteristics. This is especially important in historical works. Temurbek's friends - Amir Joku Barlos, Amir Sayfiddin Nekoz, Abbas Baha, and Davlatshah, even if they gather all their money, they cannot cover the compensation given to them. If the lexemes barlos, nekoz in this sentence indicate belonging to a certain ethnic group, the quality of bahadir is applied to brave and brave persons.

Barlos, barulas, ballos are one of the tribes that are part of the Uzbek people. In the second half of the 13th century, he moved from the banks of the Ila (Ili) river to the Kashkadarya oasis. In the 14th and 15th centuries, it played an important role in the political, economic and cultural life of the inhabitants of this oasis. Regarding the representatives of the Barlos clan, the following word is added: Amir Joku Barlos.

The interpretant of bakhsh within the anthroponym of Davlatshah bakhshi indicates a special title and employee status in the reign of Amir Temur.

It is known that there are different views on the term "bakhshi", and the explanatory dictionary mainly defines 3 different meanings:

Bakhshi [Sansk. bhikshu - Buddhist priest, sage; pray dervish]

1) Poet, poet who sings folk songs and epics from memory. Doston and terma live side by side in the repertoire of bakhshis.

2) ethnicity. A healer who heals by performing rituals, reciting prayers, and relaxing. Bakhshi, Kushnoch, Azaimkhans gathered and trained them, but he did not come, his pain worsened. "Bahram and Gulandom".

3) esq. tar. An official who oversees the calculation of funds allocated for construction in the Bukhara Khanate. (O'TIL, vol. 1, p. 180)

It is also noted in the "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan" that the word "bakhshi" is used in various ethnic groups in the following meanings: "storyteller", "kalandar", "document keeper", "secretary", "seed elder".

Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi's work "Zafarnoma" includes the names of Ardavon Bakhshi, Edi Berdi Bakhshi, Tarmachi Bakhshi, in addition to Davlatshah Bakhshi. According to Academician Sh.Sirojiddinov, in "Zafarnoma" Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi called the people who carry out writing and drawing works "Bakhshiya Turks". It is clear from this that Uzbek scribes carried out writings and drawings in Temur's palace. However, since the use of the word "bakhshi"

instead of secretary became a tradition from the Mongol khans, both terms were used in the same sense. So, if we look at it as a tradition that the secretaries were called by the name of Bakhsh during the time of Timur..."

"The following sentences mentioned in Zafarnama also help to prove Sh.Sirojiddinov's opinion: "The Fars region became musakhhar with tawabi. I gave a verdict to the Munshis and the Bakhshis, "Let the Fathnamas be!" After the Fathnamas were finished, they sent them to Khorasan region and Samarkand country and to all the regions belonging to Hazrat."

It is clear from the above points that the third meaning in "OTIL" should be filled and clarified, that is, the lexeme of bakhshi is historical as a word, not only in the Bukhara Khanate, but in history as a whole, it had the meaning of a palace official with the status of "secretary", "account keeper", "document keeper". In our opinion, the integral concept that unites all the meanings of the lexeme is its application to people who are "intelligent, open to communication, and have a high memory." In particular, it can be said that Davlatshah Bakhshi in Muhammad Ali's work is one such person.

Another important lexical-semantic groups in the historical work are words and terms related to profession: juvozchi, sahhof, naddof, morboz, jarchi, mirza, chopar, tandachi, chitgar, rikobdor, rikoboshi, bovarchi, oriz, ahangar, sayis, bakhshi (secretary, mirza, writer), malloh, bosgoch, gujarchi, muhassil, dabir, pakhsakash, archer, special healer, tawachi (tawachi). In order to realistically reflect the spirit of the era, in the works "Sardadorlar" and "Ulug' Sultanat" personal nouns representing people of the social classes of the Timurid era who are engaged in a profession or occupation are widely used, such lexemes are sharply different from the professionalism of today. That is why the lexemes in this group mainly consist of historical words (historicisms) and require an explanation for modern language speakers.

What is the connection between the smith and the potter in the city? (S.)

Naddof (Arabic to comb, comb) - a person who combed cotton or wool in the Middle Ages. He lived in separate neighborhoods in the big cities of Central Asia. Their work was mainly ginning - separating the cotton from the seed and giving it to the spinners. Naddofs were considered the poorest class of the city's population. Abu Bakr Kalavi, one of the heroes of the novel "Sarbadorlar", one of the leaders of the Sarbador movement, was an elder of the Naddoflar neighborhood.

He broke the rules, turned my face to the ground, I was ashamed in front of the bandits... (U.S.)
Tanda 1 Longitudinal, lengthwise thread for weaving fabric, weft. Both body and back are satin made of pure silk.

1) to pull out its weft in order to weave fabric; 2) to visit many times, to be a traveler somewhere. Elder Inoyat is between Margilan and Choraterak. S. Ahmad, Ufq.

A tandachi is a master tanner. (O'TIL, vol. 3, p. 662)

There were carpenters, oriz, gunsmiths, archers, blacksmiths, carpenters, road workers, trumpeters, drillers, in short, all the people who needed the life-death stage of war. (U.S.)

In B.Eshov's textbook "History of Statehood and Administration of Uzbekistan", the term "Bovarchi" is listed among the names of Amir Temur and other positions and titles of the Timurid period. If we pay attention to the dictionary meaning of the word, it is a collective name of cook, fire-lighter, taster, souffrador (that is, waiter) united under the adjective "trustworthy" (people) in Tajik. Usually, it is known from historical events that assassinations against state leaders were often carried out through food and gifts. In our opinion, in order to

prevent such situations, trusted people were taken to the palace kitchen, and in this sense they were called "trustees".

The term Oriz is defined as: "a person in the position of managing the distribution of salaries to soldiers and officials. Here it can also be understood in the sense of a treasurer.

The news of the reporter, the listener, the listeners do not match each other... (U.s.)

Narrator - 1) court position in the countries of the Muslim East. According to the order of the ruler, chroniclers wrote down all the events that took place in the country every day. 2) An officially appointed secret observer, spy, spy. According to the discursive situation expressed in the above sentence, the 2nd meaning of the lexeme of the narrator is implied.

Kulovuz are guides during military campaigns.

To listen - to listen in dialect, to hear. From this, we can say that the listener means a listener, hearer, and in a broader sense, one who listens and conveys a message by hearing. Thus, it can be seen from the comments that the story writer, the listener, the listeners in the sentence logically form a synonymous series and mean closely related meanings, i.e. people who "walk among the people and collect information". Bringing these words together gave an impetus to understand the reality and served to ensure the content of the sentence.

In general, our analysis shows that Muhammad Ali effectively used historical words in order to vividly describe the social environment of Amir Temur and the Timurid period in his works "Sarbadorlar" and "Ulug' Sultanat".

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